

Homogeneous combustion characteristics of premixed methane-air mixtures in micro-combustors

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ABSTRACT

A two-dimensional elliptic computational fluid dynamics model of micro-combustors is solved to study the effects of wall thermal conductivity on homogeneous combustion characteristics of premixed methane-air mixtures. Numerical simulations were carried out using detailed chemical reaction schemes, detailed species transport, and heat transfer mechanisms in the solid wall. We have found that the wall thermal conductivity is very important as they determine the upstream heat transfer, which is necessary for flame ignition, and the material's integrity by controlling the existence of hot spots. Large transverse and axial gradients are observed even at these small scales under certain conditions. Regarding material lifetimes, higher wall thermal conductivities reduce the wall temperature gradients and hotspots and should be preferred.

Keywords: Homogeneous combustion; Combustion characteristics; Micro-combustion; Thermal conductivity; Thermal management; Computational fluid dynamics

INTRODUCTION

Micro-combustors are increasingly studied for the catalytic and non-catalytic portable production of energy and/or heat [1]. The energy produced can be utilized by various means [2]. Examples include heat generation for remote use, such as for soldiers and space flights, thermo-electrics to produce electricity, and heat supply to micro-reactors carrying out endothermic reactions, such as steam reforming or ammonia decomposition, to produce hydrogen for portable fuel cells [3]. Because hydrocarbons possess a significantly greater energy density than traditional metal acid batteries, hydrocarbon-based micro-combustors are an enticing prospective energy source for portable power applications, such as portable electronics, laptops, cell phones, and personal heaters [4].

Unfortunately, the benefits arising at the micro-scale are overshadowed by major difficulties in creating working micro-combustors. The two primary mechanisms for quenching in micro-combustors are thermal and radical quenching [5]. Increased heat-transfer coefficients are inherent to microscales, because for a fixed Nusselt number, the heat-transfer coefficient scales with the inverse of the length scale [6]. The high heat-transfer rates increase the heat lost from the reaction, reducing the operating temperatures and causing the combustion to extinguish [7]. At the same time, the increased mass transfer within the system, coupled with the high surface-area-to-volume ratio, causes radical adsorption onto the walls, followed by radical recombination [8]. This dearth of radicals quenches the homogeneous chemistry. Another mechanism for loss of stability is blowout, which occurs when the combustor exit velocity exceeds the flame burning velocity [9]. In this case, the reaction front shifts downstream with increasing velocity and eventually exits the combustor [10]. The competition between the shifting of the reaction region and thermal quenching has been observed in

elliptic models of micro-scale systems for methane and propane [11].

Recent experiments [12] have demonstrated that it is feasible to stabilize homogeneous methane-oxygen flames between parallel plates with gaps smaller than 0.8 mm. This is accomplished by modifying the surface to make it chemically inactive, to eliminate radical quenching, and insulating the combustor, to reduce thermal quenching. The chemical inactivation process involves high-temperature annealing to heal crystal defects and surface cleaning with deionized water, hydrochloric acid, and hydrogen peroxide to remove ionic and heavy metal contaminants.

While flame propagation at the micro-scale is feasible, the interplay of kinetics and transport in flame stability and combustion characteristics of these systems is poorly understood. The inability of conducting spatially resolved measurements [13], inherent to the micro-scale, underscores the need for detailed mathematical modeling. Kaisare and Vlachos [14] have recently performed 2D simulations utilizing the boundary layer approximation in cylindrical micro-channels using detailed gas-phase chemistry and wall radical quenching chemistry to create engineering maps of wall-sticking coefficients and external heat loss coefficients that permit flame propagation [15]. The boundary layer approximation ignores axial species and energy diffusion. In those simulations, ignition was caused through sufficient preheating of premixed methane-air mixtures and the issue of self-sustained combustion could not be addressed. Furthermore, comparison of elliptic and parabolic simulations even for fast flows demonstrated that the slow gaseous heat conduction is important for quantitative prediction of ignition distance and flame stability.

In the computational fluid dynamics work of Norton and Vlachos [16], overall heat management was shown to play a critical role in determining homogeneous flame stability of methane-air mixtures

in micro-combustors. The thermal conductivity of the wall allowed both the vital upstream heat transfer for preheating the feed to the ignition temperature and detrimental heat losses to the exterior. When the thermal conductivity is too low, the upstream heat transfer through the walls is choked, and the system blows out. At the other extreme of high thermal conductivity, the wall and fluid temperature profiles flatten, causing delocalized reaction fronts and an increased external hot area for heat losses. As a result extinction is observed.

Despite previous work, there are a number of answered questions regarding homogeneous combustion characteristics at the micro-scale. In this work, the reaction and transport of methane-air mixtures in micro-combustors is studied through two-dimensional fully elliptic simulations by treating explicitly heat transfer through the wall. Numerical simulations were carried out with a two-dimensional elliptic computational fluid dynamics code in conjunction with detailed chemical reaction schemes, detailed species transport, and heat transfer mechanisms in the solid wall.

Numerical models and simulation approach

The homogeneous micro-combustor consists of two infinite parallel plates coated with platinum catalyst, 4.0 mm long, separated by a gap distance D , as shown in Figure 1. Due to the aspect ratio, the combustor is modeled as a two-dimensional system. Premixed, stoichiometric methane-air mixtures are fed to the inlet of the micro-combustor, and hot product gases exit the micro-combustor. The combustor wall is 0.2 mm thick with a constant thermal conductivity $\lambda_s = 16 \text{ W/m K}$, heat capacity $c_s = 700 \text{ J/kg K}$, and density $\rho_s = 7200 \text{ kg/m}^3$, corresponding to FeCr alloy (a common material for catalytic honeycomb combustors in power generation) [17].

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the micro-channel geometry.

The governing equations were solved for a steady laminar reactive flow in two-dimensional homogeneous micro-combustors. Computational fluid dynamics software, FLUENT[®] Release 6.3 [18], coupled with CHEMKIN [19] was used to perform these simulations. A finite-difference method is used to discretize the two-dimensional continuity, momentum, energy and species conservation equations in the fluid and the two-dimensional energy equation in the wall.

The detailed homogeneous reaction scheme, i.e., GRI-Mech 3.0 mechanism [20], was used for homogeneous reactions, which consists of 325 reversible elementary reactions involving 53 species. Species thermodynamic data were also included in the provided schemes.

Previous studies of methane-air mixtures utilizing gas-phase and surface radiation have shown that the ignition distances for combustion reactions in micro-combustors were only slightly increased by radiation [21]. The aspect ratio of the system is so high that any surface-to-surface radiation is most likely emitted and absorbed at nearly the same axial location. Therefore, radiation is omitted from the simulations performed in this work to

focus on the effect of diffusive and convective heat transport on homogeneous combustion characteristics.

The boundary conditions used in this model are as follows. A fixed flat velocity profile is assumed at the inlet. For the species and energy equations, Danckwerts boundary conditions are employed [22]; i.e., the convective portions of the equations are fixed, and the diffusive portions are calculated implicitly. At the interface between the solid and the fluid, no slip and no normal species diffusive flux boundary conditions are employed [23]. The heat flux at this interface is calculated using Fourier's law and continuity in temperature and heat flux is ensured [24]. A symmetry boundary condition is employed at the centerline between the two plates. At the exit, the pressure is specified and the remaining variables are calculated assuming far-field conditions [25], i.e., zero diffusive flux of species or energy normal to the exit. In the bulk of the wall the two-dimensional energy equation is solved. The exterior/top surface of the wall is assumed to obey Newton's law of cooling [26]. It is important to note that all the two-dimensional internal heat transfer within the fluid and the solid are calculated explicitly with the two-dimensional elliptic models without any further simplifications. The exterior convective heat-transfer coefficient is only used for the calculation of the heat flux of the exterior wall edge boundary condition. This heat-transfer coefficient lumps the details of heat loss from the micro-combustor and of the process that utilizes the heat generated by the combustor. The left and right wall edges are taken to be insulated (zero flux boundary condition) [27].

Non-uniform node spacing is employed in this work, with more nodes in the reaction region. The number of nodes varies depending on dimensions, but the simplest one consists of 80 axial nodes by 60 transverse nodes, totaling approximately 4800 nodes. Typical fluid node spacing is 50 μm in the axial direction and 8 μm in the transverse direction. Typical wall node spacing is 50 μm in the axial direction and 20 μm in the transverse direction, where the temperature does not vary (only a few nodes are placed in the transverse direction within the wall). However, as the mesh is non-uniform, these are just representative values.

The fluid density is calculated using the ideal gas law. The fluid viscosity, specific heat, and thermal conductivity are calculated from a mass fraction weighted average of species properties [28]. The species specific heat is calculated using a piecewise polynomial fit of temperature [29].

The conservation equations were solved implicitly with a two-dimensional steady-state segregated solver using an under-relaxation method. The segregated solver first solves the momentum equation, then the continuity equation, and then updates the pressure and mass flow rate. The conservation equations are then checked for convergence. Convergence is determined from the residuals of the conservation equations as well as the difference between subsequent iterations of the solution. The pressure was discretized using a "Standard" method [30]. The pressure-velocity coupling was discretized using the "Simple" method. The momentum, species, and energy equations were discretized using a first-order upwind approximation [31].

The simulations were performed on a Beowulf cluster consisting of 6 \times Xeon X5670 processors and 80 GB of RAM. When parallel processing was used, the message passing interface (MPI) was used to transmit information between nodes. In order to achieve convergence as well as compute extinction points, natural parameter continuation was implemented. The calculation time of

each simulation varied between 8 hours and several days, depending on the difficulty of the problem and the initial guess.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2. Contours of the temperature for a typical set of operating parameters.

Fig. 3. Contours of the mass fraction of methane.

For most cases studied, micro-combustors exhibit similar homogeneous combustion characteristics that are summarized in this section. Figure 2 shows contour plots of the temperature for a typical set of operating parameters. Figure 3 shows the corresponding mass fraction of methane. The entire micro-combustor is shown. The flame stabilizes in the center between the two plates. The reaction starts at the wall and travels towards the center as the flow goes downstream. Combustion occurs very rapidly, consuming most of the methane in a very small region. Complete conversion is achieved, and a significant temperature rise is observed due to the exothermicity of the reaction. The narrow flame front observed in the simulations is consistent with the computational observations by Norton and Vlachos [32]. Figure 4 depicts the temperature along the centerline and the wall interior for the same conditions. Figure 5 depicts the corresponding reaction rate at the centerline.

Fig. 4. The temperature along the centerline and the wall interior.

Fig. 5. The reaction rate at the centerline.

Three regions can be seen in these micro-combustors, namely preheating, combustion, and post-combustion or cooling, as sketched in Figures 4 and 5. The width of these regions changes as a function of operating conditions, and their distinction is not always as sharp. In the preheating region A, the wall temperature is significantly higher than the fluid temperature, so energy transfers from the wall to the fluid. The wall thermal conductivity is significantly larger than that of the fluid mixture, so most of the upstream conductive heat flux occurs within the walls of the reactor. This energy is brought upstream from the post-combustion region where walls are considerably hot. Since the methane-air mixture warms up from the wall towards the centerline, ignition occurs near the wall and the flame stabilizes at the centerline, consistent with ignition and extinction studies conducted in a micro-channel with prescribed wall temperature [33]. This ignition mode is different from the case where outside preheating is used to ignite the methane-air mixture. In the latter case, ignition occurs at the centerline.

Once the fluid reaches the ignition temperature of approximately 900 K, there is an inflection point in the temperature profile. The methane-air mixture combusts rapidly, releasing heat, which causes a sharp rise in the fluid temperature in the combustion region B. Because the walls preheat the incoming fluid, in region A, it is important that the wall temperature in region A reaches 900 K to allow fluid ignition in region B. The combustion region is relatively narrow (localized), a characteristic of highly activated reactions. Even at these relatively small scales, the transverse heat transfer within the fluid is much slower than the rate of heat release so that the fluid centerline temperature in this region approaches approximately the adiabatic flame temperature.

In the post-combustion (cooling) region C, after the reactants have been consumed, the reaction stops, the fluid cools down to the wall temperature, and the walls are cooled by exterior heat losses. There are no significant transverse or axial gradients within this region. In non-adiabatic cases, both the wall and the fluid would eventually reach room temperature in sufficiently long combustors.

In some cases, the maximum fluid temperature exceeds the adiabatic flame temperature of methane-air mixture. Traditional CSTR (continuous stirred tank reactor) or PFR (plug flow reactor) analysis suggests that this is impossible to achieve with detailed homogeneous reaction scheme. However, in this distributed model, the wall acts as a conduit for heat transfer from the hot exiting products to the cold entering reactants. This link results in a heat recycle within the system, which increases the temperatures near the inlet and allows a maximum temperature that is greater than the adiabatic flame temperature. Because of the overall energy conservation, the exiting fluid temperature is in these cases lower than the adiabatic flame temperature. Despite the micro-scales, there are still significant transverse gradients in the reaction rate and fluid temperature until nearly the end of the reaction region. Despite the fluid transverse gradients, there are no significant transverse gradients within the walls themselves in all cases studied due to the short timescale for conduction in the wall and their large aspect ratio.

Wan *et al.* [34] recently developed a micro cavity-combustor which has a strong ability in flame stabilization and is promising to be used in micro power generation apparatus for micro propulsion systems and MEMS. The analysis reveals that, for a larger thermal conductivity, the heat recirculation effect on the

fresh mixture is better, which results in higher flow velocities at the cavity exit; therefore, the flame front suffers stronger stretching effect and is splitted at lower velocities. However, for a smaller thermal conductivity, the flow velocity in the central region of far downstream becomes faster, which results in stronger flame-stretching effect and smaller flame-splitting limit. In summary, a moderate thermal conductivity is advantageous to achieve high combustion efficiency. They also developed micro-scale and meso-scale combustors with wall cavities, which have been verified to be a simple and effective way for flame anchoring [35]. Simulations suggested that the heat recirculation effect is of crucial importance to the flame blow-off limit of the meso-scale cavity-combustor. In addition, Norton *et al.* [36] demonstrated that the wall thermal conductivity plays a vital role in the flame stability and materials integrity of micro-combustors. The wall plays a dual, competing role in the overall heat transfer. On one hand, it provides a route for heat transfer from the post-combustion region to upstream for preheating that is necessary for ignition and flame stability. On the other hand, it allows exterior heat losses, which can delay ignition and cause extinction. Note that the importance of wall conduction on flame stability has been illustrated independently for Swiss roll type micro-combustors using an analytical treatment of the governing equations [37].

Fig. 6. Wall outer edge temperature profiles for different wall thermal conductivities. Low wall thermal conductivities lead to large axial wall-temperature gradients and high maximum temperatures. High wall thermal conductivity results in uniform temperature profiles without hotspots.

The material thermal conductivity affects the temperature profile within the wall and the possibility of hot spots. Figure 6 shows the temperature profiles for the outer edge of the wall for different material thermal conductivities. For low-wall-thermal-conductivity materials, significant axial temperature gradients are observed. Hotspot temperatures in excess of 2000 K can occur, an undesirable situation, as it exceeds the maximum operating temperatures of most materials of construction. Exceedingly high wall temperatures are characteristic of both micro-scale and macro-scale thermally stabilized combustors [38]. As the wall thermal conductivity increases, the wall temperature profiles become more uniform and the wall hot spot is eliminated. Despite the apparent advantages of a higher wall thermal conductivity for material stability, most materials that offer high conductance are metals, and therefore would not be inert to radical quenching. A more reasonable solution would be thicker walls of a more inert material that may have a lower thermal conductivity.

CONCLUSIONS

The homogeneous combustion characteristics of methane-air mixtures in micro-combustors were studied through two-dimensional computational fluid dynamics model. Numerical simulations were carried out with a two-dimensional elliptic computational fluid dynamics code in conjunction with detailed chemical reaction schemes, detailed species transport, and heat transfer mechanisms in the solid wall. We have found that methane-air flames can be stabilized in narrow channels but very careful design is necessary. The wall material thermal conductivity plays a competing role in homogeneous combustion characteristics. Walls transfer heat upstream for ignition of the cold incoming gases but at the same time are responsible for heat losses. Despite the small scales of these systems, large transverse gradients in temperature and species mass fractions exist in the fluid and large axial gradients in temperature may exist in the walls. Regarding material lifetimes, higher wall thermal conductivities reduce the wall temperature gradients and hotspots and should be preferred.

Acknowledgments

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